

against $\log [L]$ and limiting slopes of the curves yield ($N_{\max}/k$) values. From the knowledge of the maximum coordination number, $N_{\max}$ for each metal ion, the k value is calculated. Multiplying $\log F_0[L]$ values by the k values, yields $\log F_0[L]$ values. The $F_0[L]$ vs $[L]$ plots then give the values of formation constants^{2,3,5,7,8}.

The polarographic studies have been carried out at three temperatures, 288, 298 and 308 K and the stability constants are calculated along with thermodynamic parameters^{9,10} (Table 2).

TABLE 2—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH β -RESORCYLALDEHYDE

Metal ion	T K	$\log \beta_2$	$-\Delta G$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
MnII	288	7.05 ± 0.01	38.92	46.87	-27.26
	298	6.78 ± 0.01	38.75		
	308	6.77 ± 0.01	38.74		
CoII	288	8.35 ± 0.01	46.05	55.52	-31.79
	298	8.06 ± 0.01	46.04		
	308	7.77 ± 0.02	45.82		
NiII	288	8.64 ± 0.04	49.61	71.62	-75.72
	298	8.60 ± 0.03	49.06		
	308	8.26 ± 0.01	48.65		
CuII	288	9.56 ± 0.01	52.88	61.27	-31.33
	298	9.23 ± 0.02	52.83		
	308	9.21 ± 0.01	52.78		
ZnII	288	7.75 ± 0.04	43.07	48.76	-19.13
	289	7.79 ± 0.03	43.06		
	308	7.29 ± 0.03	43.05		

The order of overall stabilities ($\log \beta_2$) at 298 K have been found to be $Mn^{2+} < Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} < Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ ^{11,12}. The negative values of entropy for all the complexes indicate higher order in the complex molecules.

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Kinetic Study of Oxidation of Salicylidene *o*-Aminobenzoic Acid and Salicylidene *o*-Aminobenzothiol by Cerium(IV) in Acidic Medium

BALESHWAR SINGH*, V. PAL, N. SINGH

and

B. D. KANSAL

Hindu College, Moradabad

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A survey of literature has shows that much work has been done on the oxidation of various organic compounds by Ce^{IV} in acidic medium^{1,2}. Kinetics of oxidation of mandelic, *dl*-malic and lactic acid³, isobutyric acid⁴ and dicarboxylic acids⁵ by cerium(IV) have been studied by various workers. The present communication reports the kinetic study of the oxidations of Schiff base salicylidene *o*-aminobenzoic acid and salicylidene *o*-aminobenzothiol by Ce^{IV} in acidic medium which has not been studied so far.

Experimental

The kinetic runs were initiated by adding a temperature-equilibrated solution of Schiff base to a reaction vessel (at 40.0°) containing the required amount of sulphuric acid respectively, cerium(IV) sulphate solution and double-distilled water. The course of reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquot (5 ml) at different time intervals and determining the unreacted cerium(IV) by ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator.

The stoichiometry of the reaction between Ce^{IV} and these two Schiff bases was studied by the method described elsewhere². The equivalents of cerium(IV) used per mole of salicylidene *o*-aminobenzoic acid and salicylidene *o*-aminobenzothiol were found to be eight at 40° in both the cases.

Results and Discussion

The reaction has been found to obey first order reaction in $[Ce^{IV}]$ as straight lines were obtained by plotting $\log [Ce^{IV}]$ vs time for each Schiff base, and pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the slopes of these lines. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k) were directly proportional to the concentration of Schiff base. This fact is confirmed by plotting $1/k$ vs $1/[Schiff\ base]$. These plots were straight lines having an intercept on $1/k$. These facts show complex formation between Ce^{IV} and the substrates, which subsequently decomposed to the products in the rate-determining step. The reaction velocity was found to decrease with the increasing concentration of sulphuric acid.

*Chemistry Department, Government Inter College (Amroha), Moradabad-244 221.

From the study of the effect of temperature on reaction rate, activation energy and entropy of activation have been found to be 11 kcal mol⁻¹ and -46 e.u. with salicylidene *o*-aminobenzoic acid and 12 kcal mol⁻¹ and -40 e.u. with salicylidene *o*-aminobenzothiol as substrate. The following mechanism explains all the kinetic results :

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Solid State Degradation of Carbamide in Presence of Mixed Metal Oxides

RABINDRA KUMAR, B. L. BISHWAS,

J. N. TIWARI, B. KUMAR and S. BHAGAT*

University Department of Chemistry,
Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

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TRANSITION metal oxides with perovskite structure have been the subject of intensive investigations because of their interesting electrical and magnetic properties¹. The nature of defects as well as other

surface properties in many systems are yet to be studied. For example, not much is known about the catalytic properties of perovskite oxides. Presently we report the catalytic properties of LaMO₃ (M=Co, Ni) activated at different temperatures for the solid state degradation of carbamide.

Experimental

LaCoO₃ prepared by the oxalate methods², so was subjected to heat-treatment at 973, 1073, 1173 and 1273 K for 18 h. LaNiO₃ prepared³ was activated similarly. Commercial sample of carbamide was used. Excess surface oxygen (E.S.O.) and acidity of the samples were measured by the reported methods⁴.

The process and apparatus used for the kinetic study of degradation of urea were the same as adopted by Prasad and Bhagat⁴. The decomposition of a mixture of carbamide and catalyst (20 : 1) was performed at three different temperatures, viz. 413, 423 and 433 K. A plot between log (V_∞ - V_t) and time (t) was drawn, V_∞ being the volume of ammonia measured at infinite time and V_t the volume of ammonia at the time (t).

Results and Discussion

The rate constants were calculated from the initial slopes of the rate curves, -log (V_∞ - V_t) vs t (time). Energy of activation and frequency factor were calculated from the Arrhenius plots (log K vs t). Obviously the degradation of carbamide in presence of our samples obeys the first order kinetics. The values of rate constant, energy of activation and frequency factor are recorded in Table 1.

It is clear from the data (Table 1) that all the samples activated at different temperature catalyse the degradation of carbamide though their degree of catalytic activities for the thermal decomposition of urea seem to be different. Taking the values of specific rate constants in consideration, it is to be concluded that there is no regular pattern between the catalytic activities of the samples and the temperature of activation. This is also reflected from the values of energy of activation. However, the samples of LaCoO₃ activated at 1073 and 1173 K

TABLE I—KINETIC DATA FOR DEGRADATION OF CARBAMIDE

Sample	Activation temp. K	Specific rate (× 10 ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹) at			E _a kcal mol ⁻¹	log A	E.S.O./g of sample × 10 ⁻³	Acidity meq./g
		419 K	423 K	433 K				
Carbamide alone		2.78	5.28	6.75	12.25	8.00	—	—
LaCoO ₃	973	9.58	14.22	16.88	10.06	5.39	11.20	128.48
	1 073	12.27	15.35	17.90	6.65	3.54	7.12	112.42
	1 173	11.52	17.27	18.42	8.13	4.29	6.48	102.93
	1 273	8.37	12.78	17.05	12.20	6.45	5.84	98.07
LaNiO ₃	973	10.23	15.35	18.42	10.56	5.85	10.40	157.31
	1 073	13.82	16.88	18.60	4.88	2.56	7.60	144.54
	1 173	13.82	18.42	21.10	7.93	4.16	5.60	129.95
	1 273	9.58	14.32	18.42	11.52	6.26	5.44	115.24